

Graphical methods of simultaneous determination of molar absorptivity and stability constant of 1 : 1 metal complex using spectrophotometric data : Fe^{III}-5-nitrosalicylic acid complex

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Abstract : A comparative study on four well known graphical methods for simultaneous determination of molar absorptivity and stability constant of 1 : 1 metal complex using spectrophotometric data was carried out to evaluate the validity of these methods. In order to determine stability constant, Fe^{III}-5-nitrosalicylic acid system was studied in the pH range 2-3. It was found that stability constant values obtained by these methods are lower in comparison to the value obtained from a rigorous graphical method developed in this laboratory. This method is also helpful in obtaining the value of molar absorptivity simultaneously.

Keywords : Molar absorptivity, stability constant, nitrosalicylic acid, metal complex.

The spectrophotometric methods, which were quite popular in mid of twentieth century for the determination of composition as well as for the determination of stability constants of metal complexes, molecular complexes and charge transfer complexes continues to draw attention of scientist¹⁻¹⁵. There are three basic approaches for calculation of stability constant of metal complexes. One is based on continuous variations data, another is based on molar ratio data and the third one is based on graphical method. A number of review articles are available where these approaches have been dealt with. Remette has reviewed the graphical methods⁵. The graphical methods use approximations for omitting the square terms to formulate a linear equation. Usually this is achieved by keeping the ligand concentration very high so that free metal ion concentration could be neglected. Alternatively, in binomial expansions the higher terms are neglected to obtain the linear equation¹. In both the approaches results obtained are approximate. We have developed a method based on successive approximations and which does not involve omission of any term. In this paper we report a comparative account of results obtained from various graphical methods and critically examine the result to ascertain the extent of validity of these methods. The results obtained from these methods have been also compared with our

method.

For this work we have studied the Fe^{III}-5-nitrosalicylic acid system which forms a 1 : 1 complex in the pH range 1-3.

Methods :

Frank and Oswalt¹ have studied the complex formed by Fe^{III} with thiocyanate ion. If the concentration of Fe^{III} is more than that of thiocyanate ion, only 1 : 1 complex is formed.

In order to determine the stability constant of 1 : 1 complex they used the following procedure :

If M^o is the analytical concentration of metal ion and L^o is the analytical concentration of ligand, then for the reaction (1.0)

(charges are omitted for simplicity)

we can write,

$$K = \frac{[ML]}{(M^o - [ML])(L^o - [ML])} \quad (1.1)$$

If it is assumed that only one complex (1 : 1) is formed and hydrolysis has ignored; the eq. (1.1) can be rearranged as

$$[ML]^2 - (M^0 + L^0 + 1/K)(ML) + M^0L^0 = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

From which it follows :

$$[ML] = \frac{M^0L^0}{(M^0 + L^0 + 1/K)} + \frac{(M^0L^0)^2}{(M^0 + L^0 + 1/K)^2} \quad (1.3)$$

If A is the absorbance of the solution under study and ϵ_{ML} is the molar absorptivity of the complex then for 1 cm path length, one can write $A = \epsilon_{ML}[ML]$. If the higher terms in eq. (1.3) can be neglected then,

$$A = \frac{\epsilon_{ML}M^0L^0}{M^0 + L^0 + 1/K}$$

which on rearrangement reduces to

$$\frac{M^0L^0}{A} = \frac{(M^0 + L^0)}{\epsilon_{ML}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K} \quad (1.4)$$

If M^0L^0/A is plotted against $(M^0 + L^0)$, a straight line with slope $1/\epsilon_{ML}$ and intercept $1/\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K$ would be obtained.

While studying the chlorocomplexes of metal ion in aqueous solution, McConnel and Davidson² have developed the following expression for determination of stability constant of 1 : 1 complex,

$$\frac{M^0L^0}{A - A_{M^0}} + \frac{M^0}{(\epsilon_{ML} - \epsilon_M)} + \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_{ML} - \epsilon_M)} \quad (1.5)$$

where ϵ_M is the molar absorptivity of the metal and A_{M^0} is the absorbance of a solution containing the total metal ion concentration.

Ramette⁵ rearranged the Frank and Oswalt¹ eq. (1.4) in the following form

$$\frac{A}{M^0L^0} + \epsilon_{ML} \cdot K - \frac{A(M^0 + L^0)K}{M^0L^0} \quad (1.6)$$

Thus, plot of A/M^0L^0 versus $[A(M^0 + L^0)]/M^0L^0$ would be a straight line with the slope equal to K and intercept as $\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K$. Hence, it turns out to be unnecessary to know the absorptivity of the complex ion, although this quantity can be calculated as a by product in the determination of K .

Hammond⁴ from studies of series of experiments in which one of the component was in considerable excess ($L^0 \gg M^0$), and developed the following equation,

$$\frac{M^0}{A - A_M} = \frac{A}{K(\epsilon_{ML} - \epsilon_M)L} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{ML} - \epsilon_M} \quad (1.7)$$

In all these methods one or other approximation has been introduced.

In Frank and Oswalt method the term A/ϵ^2 is missing, therefore result obtained from this method is always approximate. We have derived the following equation,

$$\frac{M^0 - L^0}{A - \epsilon} + \frac{A}{(\epsilon_0)^2} + \frac{M^0 + L^0}{\epsilon_0} + \frac{1}{K\epsilon_0} \quad (1.8)$$

where, $\epsilon = M^0\epsilon_M + L^0\epsilon_L$, (1.9)

ϵ_L = molar absorptivity of ligand and

$$\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_{ML} - \epsilon_M - \epsilon_L \quad (1.20)$$

If the left hand side eq. (1.8) is plotted against $M^0 + L^0$ one will get a slope of $1/\epsilon_0$ and intercept of $1/K\epsilon_0$. From these one can calculate K . Usually the value of ϵ_{ML} is not known initially and hence nor is the value of ϵ_0 . In such a case, a trial value of ϵ_0 can be taken and approximate values of ϵ_0 and K calculated. The approximate value of ϵ_0 can be refined by successive approximations using the method of least squares¹⁶.

Results and discussion

Results obtained using all the four known methods and the method developed in this laboratory are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constant and molar absorptivity of 1 : 1 complex of Fe^{III} with 5-nitrosalicylic acid, determined by various methods

Sl. no.	Methods/ equations	ref.	log K	ϵ
1.	Frank and Oswalt	1	4.65	3.57×10^3
2.	McConnel and Davidson	2	4.95	1.79×10^3
3.	Ramette	3	4.38	1.96×10^3
4.	Hammond	4	4.70	1.90×10^3
5.	This method		5.21	2.05×10^3

It may be seen that stability constant values obtained from four known graphical methods (Fig. 1) have lower values than obtained from the method developed in this laboratory.

Frank and Oswalt method (eq. (1.4)) neglects the term A/ϵ_c^2 to get a linear equation. Considering the fact that lower value of stability constant is obtained on the omission of the term A/ϵ_{ML}^2 is not justified.

There is another problem associated with Frank-Oswalt 'slope-intercept' equation,

$$\frac{M^0L^0}{A} = \frac{(M^0 + L^0)}{\epsilon_{ML}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{ML}K}$$

Fig. 1. The graphical plots with same data on Fe^{III}-nitrosalicylic acid system are presented (i) Frank and Oswalt's method, (ii) McConnell and Davidson's method, (iii) Ramette's method, (iv) Hammond's method

From which it follows that M^0L^0/A will only show a range of values for different values of the sum ($M^0 + L^0$) provided that $(M^0 + L^0)/\epsilon_{ML}$ is not small compared to $1/\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K$ otherwise all the values of M^0L^0/ϵ_{ML} would be roughly equal $1/\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K$, and the plot would be horizontal. On the other hand, if M^0L^0/ϵ_{ML} is large compared to $1/\epsilon_{ML} \cdot K$, then the intercept cannot be precisely determined. It boils down to this, that the 'slope-intercept' method only works if $(M^0 + L^0)$ and $1/K$ are of the same order of magnitude. For very stable complexes it is hard to fix the intercept (and hence K); for very weak complexes it is hard to fix the slope ϵ .

The Frank-Oswalt¹ slope-intercept equation works quite well in the system Fe^{III}-SCN⁻, because the value of ϵ_{ML} is very large consequently the omission of the term A/ϵ_{ML}^2 is justified. Taking the data from the Frank-Oswalt work, when we calculated ϵ_{ML} and K by our procedure it was found that the value is not different from the value obtained by Frank and Oswalt.

The Ramette eq. (1.6) is a rearrangement of terms of Frank and Oswalt equation which itself is an approximation and hence in this case also lower value was obtained.

In Hammond's method⁴ the linear eq. (1.7) was obtained assuming the value of ligand is considerably higher than the metal ion concentration. However, the neglect of term free metal ion concentration definitely is not justified as is reflected in the result (Table 1).

The linear equation obtained by Davidson² also suffers from similar omission.

Thus we see that all the established methods suffer due to neglect of one or the other term, where as the method developed in this laboratory does not involve omission of any term and hence gives the best result.

Experimental

Solutions were prepared by mixing known amount of FeCl₃ (B.D.H.) and 5-nitrosalicylic acid (NO₂SA) in 1 : 1 ratio. The pH was adjusted to 2.35 ± 0.05 by adding dilute perchloric acid and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 using sodium perchlorate (B.D.H.) solution. The composition of the complex formed at pH 2.35 ± 0.05 is 1 : 1 as obtained by method of continuous variations¹⁷. A set of nine solutions were prepared and the absorbance of each solution was recorded at λ_{max} (536 nm). In this system metal ion and ligand do not absorb light in the region of interest and hence, $\epsilon_M = 0$, $\epsilon_L = 0$ and therefore $\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_{ML}$.

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